

CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY AND SELECTED PUBLIC SECTOR BANKS OF INDIA

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Abstract

Corporate Social Responsibility is a widely used concept in India in all sectors. In India banking sector especially public sector banks plays an important role, not only in developing the economy but also in serving society. This study mainly focuses on analyzing the corporate social responsibility done by the public sector banks in the last five years. The focus areas in which CSR activities are done differ from bank to bank. It has been found that generally most of the banks are focused on activities like education, health, and rural development, but they are also restricted to certain fields. There are need for better CSR activities by banks.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, Public Sector Banks, Banking Sector, Annual Reports.

Introduction

“CSR is the continuing commitment by business to behave ethically and contribute to economic development while improving the quality of the life of the workforce and their families as well as of the local community & society at large” (Singh, Srivastava & Rastogi, 2013). In the case of banks, the term is known as social banking. At present there is an increasing awareness in the banks about CSR the credit for that goes to RBI for passing a circular in the year 2007 about Corporate Social responsibility, non-financial reporting, and sustainable development.

Meaning of corporate

The word corporate originated from the Latin word 'corporatus' which means to “form into a body”. The word corporate can be defined as any activity about a corporation. Corporations are the most common form of business organization which are separate legal entities and are chartered by state. They have many legal rights. The activities that these corporations perform are known as corporate activities.

Meaning of society

The origin of the word society can be dated back to the 16th century when it originated from the Latin word “Socius” which means "companion". A society is a collection of people that are living together as a community. Society is an important factor for the success of the company as it would be existing in the society and undertaking its activities in that society only.

Meaning of responsibility

In simple terms, responsibility can be defined as a duty that one has to perform.

Definition of Corporate Social Responsibility

Corporate social responsibility means conducting business in an ethical way and the interests of the wider community and responding positively to emerging societal priorities and expectations. It is a willingness to act ahead of regulatory confrontation and balance shareholder interests against the interests of the wider community to become a good citizen.

Generally, CSR means that corporations and businesses in general while working on their main goal of maximizing their shareholders' profit should also keep in mind the societal concerns and needs and act responsibly towards the society in which they operate (Melikyan, 2010).

World Business Council for Sustainable Development has defined CSR as “the commitment of business to contribute to sustainable economic development, working with employees, their families, and the local communities”

Research Methodology

Objectives of study

- To understand the various C.S.R. activities undertaken by the selected public sector banks.
- To compute the score of C.S.R. activities undertaken by selected public sector banks.

Sample size

- To study the importance of C.S.R. here total of five public sector banks are selected.
- The banks are selected based on their high profits for the year 2014-2015. Which includes the State Bank of India, Bank of Baroda, Punjab National Bank, Canara Bank, and Union Bank of India.

Data collection

There are two sources of collection of data, primary data as well as secondary data. In this study, secondary data is used. These data are obtained from various research papers, and banks' annual reports of the last five years year from 2010-11 to 2014-15.

Tools & Techniques

The score calculated for the C.S.R. activities of each bank is as under:

If the bank undertakes the CSR activities in the domain area, then ✓ is marked, and if does not then (-) is marked. After this computation of score analysis, the selected banks undertake the maximum CSR activities in the respective year.

To calculate the score, the following formulas are used:

1. Area wise CSR performance score:

$$\frac{\textit{Total years of performace}}{\textit{Total Years}} \times 100$$

2. Year-wise CSR performance score of individual companies:

$$\frac{\textit{Area performed}}{\textit{Total areas}} \times 100$$

By using these formulas, we would be determining which area has been covered the most by the selected PSBs and which bank is the most active and the least active in performing the CSR activities.

Limitations

- The given secondary data does not provide any base for further study.
- This study includes only the information of selected five public sector banks.
- Generally selected companies provide qualitative data on CSR. So, it is difficult to collect quantitative data and compare them.
- The data collected is secondary so it has all the limitations of the secondary data.

Literature Review

Deepika Dhingra and Rama Mittal (2014) in their article entitled “CSR Practices in Indian Banking Sector” analyzed the CSR practices in the Indian banking sector. They have concluded that among the reporting banks also, some banks are making false gestures in respect of their efforts for socio-environmental concerns. Most of the Banks use CSR practices as a marketing tool and are only making token efforts towards CSR in tangential ways such as donations to charitable trusts, NGOs, sponsorship of events, etc. Very few banks have a clearly defined CSR philosophy. Most banks implement CSR in an ad-hoc manner, unconnected with their business process, and don’t state how much they spend on CSR activities. Financial Institutions can do a lot to assist efforts for social responsibility and achieve sustainability.

Vijay. P and Divya. N (December 2014) in their paper entitled “Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility Initiatives of Indian Banking Sector” analyzed the Impact of CSR in pre- and post-period implementation of the CSR concept in Indian commercial banks. Their study is based on both primary and secondary data which are collected from 135 respondents and the secondary data from the RBI website and various journals. The secondary data was taken from 2000-01 to 2012-13 in their study. The study delivers customer satisfaction, consistency, and structural changes of selected commercial banks by descriptive analysis, trend co-efficient, and Chow test. The banking industry has a significant change with CSR concept execution in India. Their

study concludes that the selected Indian banking institutions have been developed after the implementation of strong CSR concepts and they have been providing more satisfaction to bank customers.

Eliza Sharma and Dr. Mukta Mani (February 2013) in their paper entitled “Corporate Social Responsibility: analysis of Indian Commercial Banks” analyzed the corporate social responsibility (CSR) activities carried out by Indian commercial banks. Their study is based on the secondary data taken from the annual reports of the banks for the year 2009-10 to 2011-12. Variables used in the study are rural branch expansion, priority sector lending, environment protection, community welfare, women's welfare, new initiatives related to CSR, financial literacy, education, and farmers' welfare. They concluded that though the Indian banks are making efforts in the CSR areas still there is a requirement of more emphasis on CSR. There are some banks which are not even meeting the regulatory requirements. The public sector banks have the overall highest contribution to CSR activities. Private sector banks and foreign banks are still lagging in this area.

Sarita Moharana (November – December 2013) in her article entitled “Corporate Social Responsibility: A Study of Selected Public Sector Banks in India” analyzed the existing CSR practices of five nationalized banks i.e., Allahabad Bank, Andhra Bank, Bank of Baroda, State Bank of India, and UCO Bank. She has found that the selected banks are directly engaged in CSR activities mostly in the areas of Rural Development, Education, Community Welfare, and Women and Children. Her analysis shows that these banks are making efforts for the implementation of CSR, but are restricted within certain fields.

Namrata Singh, Rajlaxmi Srivastava, and Rajni Rastogi (December 2013) in their paper entitled “CSR Practices and CSR Reporting in Indian Banking Sector” try to analyze various initiatives taken by the banking sector in the current era respective to CSR and its reporting along with its future scope. They have used a Descriptive research design in their study, A Random Sampling technique was used by them for selecting the Banks for this Study in which the major players were two from the Public Sector and two from Private Sector i.e. SBI, PNB, HDFC, and ICICI selected for the study. They concluded that at present the Banking Sector performing their banking services more effectively in comparison with the past and also started working towards social banking which is Corporate Social Responsibility.

Ruchi Gupta and Gaurav Agrawal in their paper entitled “Corporate Social Responsibility: A Check on Indian Banks” for Responsible Investment analyzed the significance of CSR in the Indian banking industry and how it is unlike in comparison to other industries even in the same sector. Content analysis was done to achieve this objective. Annual reports for 2013 – 14 were collected from the official websites of banks and these banks were selected from the published list of 500 listed companies of Dun & Bradstreet. It seems that banks feel more responsible for social issues and financial inclusion is a central part of fulfilling their social responsibility while environmental issues remain unaddressed by most of them.

Data Analysis

State Bank of India

Table 1 shows Area-wise and Year-wise Performance scores and the rank assigned to them by the State Bank of India.

No.	VARIABLES	YEARS					TOTAL	Area wise Performance score (In %)	RANK
		2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15			
1	Supporting Education	√	√	√	√	√	5	100	1
2	Supporting Health	√	√	√	√	√	5	100	1
3	Rural Development	√	-	-	-	-	1	20	4
4	Women's Empowerment	√	-	-	-	-	1	20	4
5	Supporting Girl Children & Child Development	√	√	-	-	-	2	40	3
6	Assistance to poor and underprivileged	√	√	√	√	-	4	80	2
7	Entrepreneur Development Programs	√	√	√	√	-	4	80	2
8	Vocational guidance and livelihood creation	√	-	-	-	√	2	40	3
9	Environment Protection	√	√	√	√	-	4	80	2
10	Natural Calamities	√	√	√	√	√	5	100	1
11	Clean Energy	-	√	-	-	-	1	20	4
12	Supporting sanitation	-	-	-	-	√	1	20	4
TOTAL		10	8	6	6	5	35		
Year-wise performance score (In %)		83	66	50	50	41			
RANK		1	2	3	3	4			

- The main focus areas under the period of study for SBI in CSR are Education, Health, and Natural calamities. The bank has also focused on areas like Entrepreneur Development Programs, environmental protection, and the poor and underprivileged. In the years 2010-11, the bank has covered the majority of CSR activities. SBI seems to reduce their focused areas over time.

Bank of Baroda

Table 2 shows Area-wise and Year-wise Performance scores and the ranks assigned to them by Bank of Baroda.

No.	VARIABLES	YEARS					TOTAL	Area wise Performance score (In %)	RANK
		2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15			
1	Education	-	-	√	√	√	3	60	3
2	Health	-	-	√	√	√	3	60	3
3	Rural Development	√	√	√	√	√	5	100	1
4	Women Welfare	-	-	√	√	-	2	40	4
5	Social welfare activities	-	-	√	√	-	2	40	4
6	Entrepreneur skill development	-	√	√	√	√	4	80	2
7	Self - employment	√	√	√	√	√	5	100	1
8	Environment protection	-	-	-	-	√	1	20	5
9	Socio-economic Development	-	-	-	-	√	1	20	5
TOTAL		2	3	7	7	7	26		
Year-wise performance score (In %)		22	33	77	77	77			
RANK		3	2	1	1	1			

- The main focus areas under the period of study for BOB in CSR are Rural Development and Self-employment. The Bank has also focused on entrepreneurial skill development. The BOB has increased their areas covered by the time and there is adoption of huge CSR activities in the year 2012-13.

Punjab National Bank

Table 3 shows Area-wise and Year-wise Performance scores and the rank assigned to them by Punjab National Bank.

No.	VARIABLES	YEARS					TOTAL	Area wise Performance score (In %)	RANK
		2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15			
1	Education Initiatives	√	√	-	-	√	3	60	3
2	Health & Social Initiatives	√	√	√	√	√	5	100	1
3	Rural Development	√	√	√	√	√	5	100	1
4	Women's Empowerment	√	√	-	-	√	3	60	3
5	Medium and small-scale Industries	√	√	-	-	√	3	60	3
6	Financial literacy	√	-	√	√	√	4	80	2
7	Agriculture development	√	√	√	√	√	5	100	1
8	Green Initiatives	-	√	√	√	√	4	80	2
9	Sports	√	√	√	√	√	5	100	1
10	Natural calamities	-	-	-	√	√	2	40	4
11	Supporting Youth and Weaker section	-	-	-	-	√	1	20	5
TOTAL		8	8	6	7	11	40		
Year-wise performance score (In %)		72	72	54	63	100			
RANK		2	2	4	3	1			

- The main focus areas under the period of study for PNB in CSR are Health and Social Initiatives, Rural development, agriculture development, and sports. The bank has covered the majority of focus areas in the year 2014-15.

Canara Bank

Table 4 shows Area-wise and Year-wise Performance scores and ranks assigned to them by Canara Bank.

No.	VARIABLES	YEARS					TOTAL	Area wise Performance score (In %)	RANK
		2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15			
1	Education	-	-	√	√	√	3	60	1
2	Health	-	-	√	√	√	3	60	1
3	Rural development	-	-	-	-	√	1	20	3
4	Women Welfare	-	-	√	√	√	3	60	1
5	Charities	-	-	√	√	-	2	40	2
6	Social Welfare & Relief	-	-	√	√	-	2	40	2
7	Energy Conservation	-	-	√	√	-	2	40	2
8	Skill Development	-	-	√	√	√	3	60	1
9	Art & Culture	-	-		√	√	2	40	2
10	Chief Minister's Relief funds	-	-	-	√	-	1	20	3
11	Financial literacy	-	-	-	-	√	1	20	3
12	Rural development	-	-	-	-	√	1	20	3
13	Sports	-	-	-	√	-	1	20	3
14	Persons with disabilities & old age	-	-	-	-	√	1	20	3
15	Poverty & Nutrition	-	-	-	-	√	1	20	3
16	Environment protection	-	-	-	-	√	1	20	3
TOTAL		-	-	7	10	10	27		
Year-wise performance score (In %)		-	-	46	66	66			
RANK		-	-	2	1	1			

- The main focus areas under the period of study for Canara Bank in CSR are Health, Education, Skill development, and Women's welfare. The Bank has maintained a level of activities in CSR for 2013-14 and 2014-15.

Union Bank of India

Table 5 shows area-wise and year-wise Performance scores and ranks assigned to them by the Union Bank of India.

No.	VARIABLES	YEARS					TOTAL	Area wise Performance score (In %)	RANK
		2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15			
1	Education	√	√	-	√	√	4	80	2
2	Health	√	-	√	-	-	2	40	3
3	Rural development	√	√	√	√	√	5	100	1
4	Financial literacy	√	√	-	-	-	2	40	3
5	Self-employment	√	√	√	√	√	5	100	1
6	Sanitation	-	√	-	√	√	3	60	3
7	Natural Calamity	-	-	√	√	√	3	60	3
8	Persons with disabilities & old age	-	-	-	√	√	2	40	3
TOTAL		5	5	4	6	6	26		
Year-wise performance score (In %)		62	62	50	75	75			
RANK		2	2	3	1	1			

- The main focus areas under the period of study for UBI in CSR are rural development and self-employment. The Bank has maintained a level of activities in CSR for 2013-14 and 2014-15.

Conclusion

- The focus areas in which CSR activities are done differ from bank to bank. It has been found that generally most of the banks are focused on activities like education, health, and rural development during the period of study. It is also found that banks are restricted to certain fields. There are need for better CSR activities by banks.
- It is found that from the years 2012-13 to 2014-15 selected PSBs performed their CSR activities better than the past two years.
- SBI is more focused on Education and health, BOB has covered rural development and self-employment, PNB is focused on Health and Social Initiatives, Rural development, agriculture development, and sports-related activities. Canara Bank has not disclosed CSR-related activities in annual reports of the years 2010-11 and 2011-12, but after that year bank has covered most of the CSR-related activities and their focus is on Health, Education, Skill development, and Women welfare-related activities. UBI in CSR activities has covered rural development and self-employment.
- Finally, the analysis shows that selected PSBs are implementing CSR activities but still there is a requirement of more emphasis on CSR.

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